

CHIME Selective Compression: baseline and mission extension

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ABSTRACT

Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) mission aims to enhance the Copernicus space component with precise spectroscopic measurements composed of 250 continuous narrow spectral bands (10 nm) in VNIR/SWIR spectral domain (400-2500 nm) sampled at 30 m over a swath of ~130 km. CHIME mission baseline is systematic acquisitions during the daylight part of the orbit, over all land surfaces including islands greater than 100 km², coastal zones within 370 km distance from land. The amount of data to be transmitted to the ground is very large, making on-board data reduction mandatory.

Considering the significant presence of clouds, a selective cloud compression has been designed and is currently under development. The principle is to detect clouds and then to compress with a lower data rate compared to the clear pixels. The compressor is based on the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard with evolution for selective compression as a function of the pixel class. The upcoming version of this standard (CCSDS 123.0-B-3) will integrate this selective compression feature, in part thanks to the work done for CHIME.

The principle of this two-classes selective compression is presented together with the improvement of data reduction. The CHIME data reduction scheme is configurable for acquisitions along the orbit, leading to a flexible processing. It gives opportunity to extend applications. The paper presents an example of CHIME mission extension to detect “anomalies” over oceans that could be possible with on-board configurable selective compression

INTRODUCTION

The amount of data acquired by the Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) is very large (4.5 Gbps), uncompressed data implies a Terabits memory volume order of magnitude per orbit. (Background and latest status of the mission was recently summarised in [1]). Therefore, for both on-board memory management and compatibility of current downlink solution, on-board optimized compression is required. The systematic acquisitions performed by CHIME will lead to a significant presence of clouds hiding the Earth surface in the images. Since CHIME mission is focusing on terrestrial applications, efficient cloud screening and potential removal became a key interest since the beginning of CHIME development. As a result, it was decided to implement a selective compression as the baseline for on-board data reduction. The principle is to detect the opaque clouds and then to compress with a lower data rate compared to the clear pixels. It corresponds to a two-classes selective compression. The first step of the data reduction is the cloud detection: a Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach has been selected for CHIME; it is presented in the section “cloud detection”.

The output cloud map is then provided to the compressor. The compressor is based on the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 recommended standard [2] for a low-complexity data compression applied to multispectral and hyperspectral sensors, with an evolution of the prediction stage which is detailed in the “selective compression” section. An overview of the implementation for CHIME is also presented.

Performance obtained at CHIME Preliminary Design Review (PDR) showed the need for near-lossless compression together with the benefit of selective cloud compression (section “performance”).

The SVM and selective compressor are flexible in their configuration settings. It leaves the possibility to detect other features and the selective compressor can be used to adjust the transmission to the ground. The current study led by ESA and involving THALES ALENIA SPACE is presented - the aim is to confirm the potential CHIME mission extension to detect anomalies over the oceans, thanks to an appropriate configuration of the Data Processing Unit (DPU) on-board CHIME for acquisitions outside the baseline duty cycle.

CLOUD DETECTION

For the purpose of selective compression, the aim of cloud detection is to detect opaque cloud hiding the ground, translucent clouds (e.g. cirrus clouds) still contain ground information and thus must be considered as “clear” pixels. During CHIME Phase B2, a trade-off has been led for on-board cloud detection. The objective was to find a flexible approach capable of limiting the false positive rate, implementable on FPGA and able to process on the flow the high acquisition data rates (1.5 Gbps per chain).

SVM, threshold method and Artificial Intelligence (AI) Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for which THALES ALENIA SPACE is involved [3] have been considered. However, the high memory and computations required by the CNN was not compatible with the CHIME on-board capacity and therefore the CNN technic has been put aside from the experiments. The threshold method [4, 5, 6] can be seen as a “physical” approach as it allows to discriminate the clouds from the other on-ground features by means of threshold on dedicated spectral bands, and on specific band combinations to discriminate high reflective surface from clouds (e.g. snow). The SVM approach allows to separate the pixels into two classes (clear or cloud) in a N-dimension space. A supervised machine learning approach is used in order to find the optimal hyperplane separating the two classes. The training stage is performed on-ground and thus has no impact on the on-board processing. The performance of these two cloud detection methods has been firstly assessed on the Landsat cloud data base “SPARCS” [7]. The results have been presented at *OBPDC 2020* [8]. The SVM approach has been adopted, for its short advantage on the false positive error rate, but also for its performance already proven on multispectral ground segments and for its high adaptability to evolutions (e.g. new bands among the hyperspectral cube for detection improvement).

The cloud detection scheme for CHIME is presented Fig.1. The SVM model is drawn from the physical approach, with in particular the possibility to include band ratios and indexes. The configurable DPU can consider out of the spectrum of ~250 spectral bands up to 8 bands, 3 band ratios and 3 index, leading to a flexible SVM model. In order to be insensitive to solar illumination, a radiometric conversion in Top-Of-Atmosphere reflectance is previously applied on the bands selected for cloud detection. The SVM cloud detection is pixel-based and provides as output a 2D binary “raw” cloud map which identifies a hyperspectral pixel as cloudy or not. In order to reduce the false positive detection (i.e. clear pixels detected as cloud), a morphological filtering (erosion followed by dilatation) is applied to the raw cloud map. The radius of the filter can be set up to 15 pixels (filter mask 31 x 31) and the structuring element is fully flexible (filter mask provided by settings). The filtering stage implies a buffering since requires the information from the neighborhood. The morphological filtering allows also the removal of small clouds considered as not useful for selective cloud compression (see section “Performance”).

The configurable setting allows to exploit the precise spectrometric measurements of CHIME for the detection. The principle is to define and to train a SVM model on-ground with representative data and then to upload on-board the parameters.

Fig. 1. Principle of CHIME cloud detection

The training data are representative hyperspectral images for various landscapes and cloud features associated to a reference cloud map (what we call a cloud data base). During the commissioning phase, it is planned to update the cloud data base with real data. But for performance assessment and first settings before the launch, a hyperspectral cloud data base is needed.

Cloud data bases are available for multispectral data, but we did not find a hyperspectral cloud data base. Therefore THALES ALENIA SPACE has started to build a data base with PRISMA acquisitions [10]. Indeed, PRISMA is an operational satellite sensor whose characteristics are close to CHIME (VIS/SWIR spectral domain, continuous 10 nm spectral bands, 30 m. spatial sampling). PRISMA products are available on-demand ([ASI | Agenzia Spaziale Italiana](https://asi.esa.int)). The associated cloud maps included within PRISMA product are not precise enough, therefore THALES ALENIA SPACE built a “reference” cloud map using in-house SVM training tool.

CHIME program includes an End-to-End image simulator managed by ESA whose development is well-advanced. It includes a scene generator which allows to produce scenes of various landscapes and with several type of (opaque) clouds. The cloud “simulation” leads to control the size and most particularly to get an unquestionable reference cloud map. With such images and associated reference cloud map that should come soon, a reliable performance assessment of the cloud detection will be possible.

SELECTIVE COMPRESSION

The cloud map identifies pixel as cloudy or clear. It applies to all the bands, i.e. a pixel is considered cloudy in the full spectral range (hyperspectral pixel).

The compressor is based on the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 recommended standard. Three schemes have been studied for the two-classes selective compression and evaluated on AVIRIS and CHIME simulated images [8]: applying a pre-quantization before compression, forcing the prediction residual to zero for cloud pixel (Residual To Zero) or applying a class-dependent error settings (Different Absolute Error).

The pre-quantization scheme operates with the standard compressor without any change, but showed lower data rate reduction compared to the other schemes. The Residual To Zero was the most efficient for cloud data rate reduction, but at the price of a loss of cloud information. The Different Absolute Error (DAE) has been adopted for CHIME since it allows a full spatial and spectral quality control with good compression performance.

The concept of the DAE compressor is to apply a different error setting as a function of the pixel class. It acts on the quantizer within the prediction loop in the near-lossless CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard (Fig.2). For CHIME, the quantizer step size is controlled via the absolute error limit. The absolute error setting is band-dependent according to the standard but becomes class-dependent thanks to the DAE. This leads to a flexible scheme able to compress without any loss, or in near-lossless mode a full control per band of the errors on the cloudy and on the clear pixels.

But the DAE requires an adaptation of the standard decompressor with the cloud map and the associated cloud absolute error settings encoded and transmitted on ground thanks to supplementary information tables allowed by the standard (Fig.3).

Fig. 2. Identification of the DAE evolution within CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard

Considering the implementation constraints on CHIME, the number of prediction bands is fixed to 3, the reduced-prediction mode is considered with two local sum types: Narrow neighbour-oriented and Narrow column-oriented. In baseline Narrow neighbour-oriented is considered since CHIME instrument include an equalization processing to compensate for the detector non-uniformity response with the aims to improve compression performance. Narrow column-oriented can be selected via settings in case of poor compensation. The block-adaptive encoder has been selected with block size that can be adjust to 32 or 64; it could allow a data rate lower than 1 bit par pixel especially for large errors on clouds.

IMPLEMENTATION ON CHIME

CHIME instrument is composed of three spectrometers to cover a swath of ~130 km. Each spectrometer earth acquisition is compressed independently on the flow thanks to independent processing chains implemented within the DPU.

The DPU partitions the input data flux in segment so-called HyperSpectral Containers (HSC) of 64 frames (Fig.3). The selective compression applies independently on the HSCs leading to limit a potential data corruption to the affected HSC in the reconstructed image. The cloud detection applies also on the HSC but the filtering stage needs to keep information of the previous and the following HSC.

The compressed data is packetized thanks to CCSDS.133 standard.

The settings of data reduction are shared between adjustable and dynamic parameters. The adjustable parameters are supposed to be stable within an orbit and for several consecutive orbits. This is the case for instance of the local sum type. They can be changed when DPU is in standby mode.

Dynamic parameters can be changed within an orbit. Conceptually, the dynamic parameters are included in several tables that are uploaded in the DPU. The tables identification is controlled by the on-board computer and passed to the DPU within the Instrument Source Packets (ISP). It can change by HSC but in practice it is not expected to change many times during the orbit. The dynamic parameters are the SVM model and filtering for cloud detection, and the two-class errors for the compressor. It must be noticed that the solar zenith angle and the distance Earth-Sun as needed for TOA reflectance conversion is computed by the CHIME on-board computer and transmitted for each HSC to the DPU through the ISP.

The 3 independent data threads related to the 3 spectrometers are processed by a single FPGA.

Fig. 3. Data reduction scheme on-board CHIME

PERFORMANCE

The performance assessed at CHIME PDR is presented in this section. The performance will be refined in the frame of CHIME Critical Design Review (CDR) scheduled beginning of 2025.

Hyperspectral images

For the CHIME PDR exercise, the hyperspectral images have been simulated with the CHIME Observation Performance Simulator (OPSI) Version 1. The scenes come from “TOA maps” provided by ESA and processed through the simulator in order to get radiometric, spectral and geometric representative images at the time of the PDR. The simulations have been sized to get a representative swath processed by the DPU (~45km – 1500 pixels) with pixel dynamic of 16 bits. These scenes offer a variety of landscapes (land, rural, urban, island, sea, mountain, desert) for some with clouds (Fig.4).

Fig. 4. Simulated scenes considered for the data reduction exercise (Credit ESA).

Standard compression performance

The selective DAE compressor benefits from the CCSDS standard and allows to compress without any loss by simply setting the error for the two-classes and for all bands to zero. The lossless compression ratio varies from 2.17 for urban image to 2.6 for sea, and is in average 2.3 for all images.

Near-lossless is achieved by setting the same errors to the two-classes. The errors have been set according to ESA recommendations that were a low compression noise and as much as possible independent of the signal.

Together with ESA, we led a study taking benefit of the availability of the instrument radiometric noise model (NEDL); we considered several (band-dependent) error settings as function of the NEDL, and applied to a subset of simulated images including typical, high and low radiances. The histograms of the errors per band have been analysed together with visual inspection. The conclusion led to a setting of error corresponding to $q_z=2*NEDL @ L_{min}$, where q_z is the quantizer step size within the predictor stage [2], and L_{min} corresponds to the minimum radiance as specified for CHIME.

With this setting, the near-lossless compression ratio varies from 4.3 for urban image to 6.4 for sea, and is in average 5.0 for all images.

Cloud detection performance

No hyperspectral cloud data base was available at PDR. Therefore we relied on the multispectral Landsat 8 data base "SPARCS" [7] to train a reduced SVM model (since multispectral data) composed of 5 bands, 1 band ratio and 2 indexes (Desert and Sand Index & Normalized Difference Snow Index). Performance of this model, in particular False Positive error rate, has been presented at *OBPDC 2020* [8].

This model has been applied to the simulated Hyperspectral images. No quantitative assessment of the cloud detection performance has been possible for these scenes since cloud reference was not available at this time. The results are visually good, showing the applicability of the SVM to different source of images. The filtering stage removes some ambiguities and possible false positive (see examples Fig.5). But the cloud reference is implicitly not needed for clear images due to the absence of clouds: for all clear images, even in image where snow was present, no cloud has been detected leading to a good result regarding the false positive what was the goal for the selective cloud compression embarked on CHIME.

Fig. 5. Two examples of cloud detection (left, right) with original scene (top), the raw cloud map (centre), the cloud map after a filtering with a disk of radius 6 (bottom left clouds=1%, bottom right clouds=22%) .

Selective cloud compression performance

Selective cloud compression performance has been assessed with 2 kinds of settings for clear class:

1. clear pixels with lossless compression
2. clear pixels with same error settings as for standard near-lossless compression

Assuming cloud radiance is high, the errors for the cloud class have been set in order $q_z=4 \cdot \text{NEDL} @ L_{\text{max}}$, where L_{max} corresponds to the maximum radiance as specified for CHIME.

Selective cloud compression performance is intrinsically dependent on the presence of clouds. But the available images were partially cloudy (Fig.4), so we extended to higher coverage by duplication of cloudy areas within the images (Fig.6). Selective cloud compression performance (compression ratio and data rate) is summarized Fig.7. The curves show the benefit of selective cloud compression increasing with cloud coverage.

The first observation from the curves is that the standard compression performance is decreasing when cloud coverage is increasing, showing the high signals with high transitions are more difficult to compress. The selective compression reverses the inclination with an increasing CR with cloud coverage, displaying a noticeable gain from 20% of clouds. For 54% of clouds which is close to the cloud coverage on the Earth surface over a year, we observe a reduction of the data rate by around 25%.

Fig. 6. Cloud coverage artificially increase Top: image, bottom: Map from cloud detection
 Left : cloud map with 34% of clouds - Right cloud map with 54% of clouds

Fig. 7. Selective cloud compression performance (blue) compared with standard compression (orange) as function of cloud coverage - Left: lossless compression of clear pixel - Right: Near-lossless compression of clear pixel.

However, the cloud coverage number as a whole is not sufficient to derive the selective cloud compression performance; the repartition of the clouds within the image plays a role in data reduction. Indeed, for the same coverage, the selective cloud compression performance is lower for small clouds spread over the image compared to large clouds. The reason is that the prediction is less performant when lot of high variations are occurring within an image. In the case of cloud selective compression, this phenomena is amplified by the large difference of the errors settings between clear and cloud classes. Therefore we recommend, in particular for cloud selective compression, to not include small clouds (making possible by the morphological filtering implemented on CHIME), and to keep a reasonable difference of the absolute errors between the two classes.

SELECTIVE COMPRESSION AND CHIME MISSION DUTY CYCLE EXTENSION

The selective compressor together with the SVM flexible model implemented in CHIME DPU leave the possibility to detect and to process other features. One concept would be to enable a partial or systematic daytime extension over oceans.

The principle is to adapt the data reduction parameter settings for acquisitions over oceans to detect and to transmit “anomalies” and to highly compress the non-useful acquisitions.

The tracked anomalies are currently being defined, among typically marine debris (including plastic), sargassum or natural organic materials [9].

The SVM detection will not change, only the settings for the purpose. As for the cloud, the training is performed on ground, and the settings will be uploaded through the parameter tables. The filtering stage differs from cloud detection on the fact that different filters are used for erosion and dilatation step, the dilatation filter being large whereas erosion one small. Such configuration allows to extend the region around the detected “anomaly” in order for the end-users to get the context around the detected “anomalies”. The output of the detection stage is still a map with regions of interest.

The selective compressor is set with no error or small errors for the regions of interest and large errors for the remaining ocean pixels.

The study is currently in progress. Several satellite sub-systems are impacted by the increased data rate and need analysis (e.g. mass memory, thermal control ...). The application of the concept on the data processing has been functionally verified by THALES ALENIA SPACE. The training and the image performance are part of ESA activities. This study should be finalised at CHIME CDR.

This study is an example of mission and application extension that configurable selective compression makes possible.

CONCLUSION

Selective compression has been a candidate for data reduction of satellite acquisitions for many years. It appears very interesting and applicable for the Earth observation missions with high data rates and continuous acquisitions as for the Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME).

The selective compression is applied to opaque clouds since not considered as useful for CHIME applications. The selective cloud compression design is established, and is currently under development.

This data reduction scheme that will be implemented on-board CHIME is presented in this paper together with the performance assessed at the Preliminary Design Review of CHIME. Noticeable gain is observed from 20% of clouds and naturally increases with cloud coverage – going to a data rate reduction of 25% compared to standard compression for 50% of large clouds. The compressor is based on the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard with evolutions in the predictor stage, that we called “Difference Absolute Error”. It gives an additional spatial selectivity to the compressor already flexible in spectral dimension. The upcoming version of this standard (CCSDS 123.0-B-3) will natively integrate this selective compression feature, in part thanks to the work done for CHIME.

The detection based on SVM approach and the selective compression are configurable for acquisitions along the orbit, leading to a flexible processing. It gives opportunity to extend applications. The paper presents an example of CHIME mission extension to detect anomalies over oceans that could be possible with on-board configurable selective compression.

Acknowledgments

The work leading to these results has been funded by ESA through the CHIME pre-development study of CHIME A/B1 and CHIME B2/C/D contract. THALES ALENIA SPACE in France is PRIME. The Data Processing Unit which includes data reduction is developed by THALES ALENIA SPACE in Spain with University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria - Institute for Applied Microelectronics (IUMA) in charge of the compressor IP. The authors thank:

- Luis Rafael Berrojo Valero, Pedro Rodriguez Perochena, Joseph Purnell and Victor Del Estal Fernández from THALES ALENIA SPACE in Spain

- Roberto Sarmiento, Yubal Barrios and Antonio Jose Sanchez Clemente from IUMA

for the fruitful discussions, team spirit and the implementation of the selective cloud compression for CHIME.

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